

DELIVERABLE 5.5

SHORT REPORT ON MOST VALID FOOD-RELATED EXPLOITATION SCHEMES

AUTHORS

**Guglielmino Lina
Silvestro Annalaura
31.01.2024**

PROJECT ACRONYM:	FoodCLIC
PROJECT NUMBER:	101060717
WORK PACKAGE NUMBER AND TITLE:	WP5 Communication, dissemination and exploitation
LEAD BENEFICIARY:	CARIPLO
WORK PACKAGE LEADER:	CARIPLO & SURREY
RELEVANT TASK:	5.4 Development and implementation of exploitation plan
DISSEMINATION LEVEL:	Public
DUE DATE (MONTH):	17
VERSION:	V01

Funded by
the European Union

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION.....	4
2. METHODOLOGY.....	5
3. REVIEW OF EXISTING RELEVANT EXPLOITATION SCHEMES.....	7
4. FOCUS ON INVESTMENTS SCHEMES: IMPACT FINANCE AS INSTRUMENT TO SUPPORT OUTCOME-BASED PROJECTS.....	11
5. OUTCOME-BASED CONTRACTING CASE STUDIES IN THE AGRI-FOOD BUSINESS SECTOR 34	
6. CONCLUSION	41
REFERENCES	43

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 REPORT OBJECTIVE

The present report has the objective to provide an overview of exploitation plans in the European context, with a particular focus on initiatives related to the food sector. The main objective of this analysis is to identify and evaluate the exploitation strategies developed by projects funded by the European Commission. Adopting a data-driven and critical analytical approach, the report seeks to provide insights into the characteristics and specificities of the exploitation plans analysed through a thorough examination of these practices.

In order to unravel the potential correlation between positive impact outcomes achieved by a European project and investment mechanisms, an in-depth exploration of impact finance as a tool to support outcome-based projects was undertaken. This research sought to identify how financial instruments are aligned with impact-oriented projects within the European landscape. The research included an examination of impact finance instruments and an assessment of how impact finance could be used strategically as a funding mechanism to support initiatives that deliver tangible and positive outcomes. By delving into the intricacies of impact finance in the context of outcome-based projects, the study aimed to illuminate the intersection between impactful project outcomes and the financial instruments critical to their sustainability and scalability.

1.2 DELIVERABLE STRUCTURE

The present report is structured across six Chapters and aims to explore valid and insightful food-related exploitation schemes and impactful financial models with a focus on Outcome-Based Projects (OBPs) in the agri-food sector. The Deliverable starts with the Introduction in Chapter 1, setting the purpose by providing an overview of the deliverable's objectives. Chapter 2 outlines the Methodology employed in the research, outlining the strategic approach adopted to scrutinize the subject matter effectively, while Chapter 3 reviews relevant exploitation schemes with a focus on food-related European projects. A deep dive on several impact-oriented investment schemes is provided in Chapter 4, which explores Impact Finance, alternative instruments and the concept of Blended Finance. Chapter 5 presents Outcome-Based Contracting (OBC) case studies in the agri-food sector, offering valuable insights. The document concludes in Chapter 6 with a summarized overview and conclusive findings. The deliverable is supported by References and Websites sections, enhancing its credibility and providing additional resources.

2. METHODOLOGY

The preparation of this document employed a comprehensive methodology that embraced a multifaceted approach. This approach involved a thorough exploration and analysis of exploitation plans within the European context, with a specific focus on impact investing tools to support projects related to the food sector. Additionally, the methodology emphasized an in-depth examination of the Outcome-Based Contracting (OBC) model, contributing to a holistic understanding of strategic frameworks and financial mechanisms crucial for the success and sustainability of initiatives in the food-related domain. The analysis illustrated in this report were conducted by Cariplo Factory, with the support of the Tiresia Research Center of Politecnico di Milano.

The first phase consisted of a thorough desk analysis of the Cordis database¹, identifying and selecting projects according to specific criteria. These criteria were used to find the most appropriate Exploitation Plans (EPs) in terms of alignment with coherent themes related to education, food and sustainable practices.

The process of identifying and selecting Exploitation Plans within the Cordis platform involved a systematic approach. First, the 'Collection' filter was set to 'Projects' to narrow down the search. Next, the 'Domain' filter was applied, and the 'Food and Natural Resources' option was selected. The 'Field of Science' parameter was set to 'Agricultural Sciences' and 'Social Sciences'. This filtering resulted in a subset of 72 projects. On this basis, a careful review of the projects was then carried out, taking into account both the objectives of the projects and the presence of a final version of the Exploitation Plan. Through this comprehensive analysis, a curated selection of eight exploitation plans was identified. This rigorous process ensured the inclusion of projects that not only met the specified criteria, but also demonstrated a clear articulation of their exploitation plans in the final project documentation.

Given the social and environmental impact that FoodCLIC aims to achieve, focused research on impact finance tools was included to understand the potential of financial mechanisms and instruments that fall under the umbrella of impact finance to support initiatives in the agri-food sector. The analysis is based on an extensive literature review (both academic and practitioner literature as well as other available sources) and an original compilation of secondary data from existing databases and sources. First, the analysis of the concept is based on a specific definition of impact finance. An overview of the state of the market at global, European and Italian level was also provided. Secondly, a review of the main instruments considered under the umbrella of impact finance has been carried out. These can be divided into three main groups: debt-based, equity-based and public-private partnerships.

The financial aspect was also addressed through a review of impact finance practices, providing a deeper understanding of the economic implications associated with these plans. In addition, case studies of OBC were analysed and interviews with agribusiness experts were planned and conducted

¹ [CORDIS | European Commission \(europa.eu\)](https://cordis.europa.eu/)

to gain valuable insights from key stakeholders and provide qualitative data to complement the quantitative findings.

A significant aspect of the methodology involved delving into OBC case studies within the Agri-food sector. This included an analysis of challenges and potential benefits associated with OBC in this sector. To provide a structured framework, a taxonomy of the most attractive business models in the Agri-food sector was developed, facilitating a systematic classification for further evaluation.

3. REVIEW OF EXISTING RELEVANT EXPLOITATION SCHEMES

This report presents a comprehensive analysis of eight notable European food-related projects – *SIM4NEXUS*, *Circular Agronomics*, *Climefish*, *Seefoodtomorrow*, *Pro-enrich*, *Gates*, *Newbe*, and *AUTHENT-NET*. The analysis focuses on various dimensions proposed because considered relevant and insightful for shaping FoodCLIC's Exploitation Plan. Such dimensions aimed to specifically underscore interesting and innovative ways to exploit project results. Dimensions of analysis were related to RESULTS and EXPLOITATION, as following:

Results:

- Presence of business models/outcomes in the market among Key Exploitable Results
- Presence of tools for impact assessment

Exploitation:

- Proposal of impact finance instruments
- Proposal of innovative exploitation tools (e.g., hackathons, open windows, innovation days)
- Identification of other interesting themes
- Links with other European projects

3.1 PROJECT ANALYSIS

The projects are outlined below with a brief introduction to their main objectives described on Cordis platform, followed by the dimension of analysis that has yielded interesting and useful insights.

SIM4NEXUS (final), Jun 2016 – Jun 2020

SIM4NEXUS aims to enhance the integrated management of the Land-Food-Energy-Water-Climate Nexus, a complex system with interconnected components. Addressing barriers to resource efficiency in Europe, such as policy inconsistencies and knowledge gaps, the project will develop innovative methodologies. This includes complexity science approaches for integrating thematic models, a Geoplatfrom for data integration, a Knowledge Elicitation Engine for strategy integration, and a web-based Serious Game for immersive visualization and understanding of policies at various scales. The Serious Game will be validated through ten case studies and further developed at European and Global levels for demonstration and education, accompanied by a robust business plan for post-project exploitation.

Identification of other interesting themes

In the context of the project's exploitation strategy, the partners are categorized into distinct roles based on their involvement and responsibilities. Gold members are actively responsible for the exploitation process, taking a leading role in leveraging intellectual property rights (IPR) assets and ensuring continued development. Silver members are actively engaged in the exploitation effort, contributing to the process with specific IPR assets and collaborative input. Bronze members, while not directly responsible for leading the exploitation, are involved in specific aspects and may possess relevant IPR assets. Those not interested in continuing the exploitation are acknowledged as non-participating entities. This tiered approach ensures a structured and collaborative effort, delineating roles and responsibilities among the project partners to optimally exploit and capitalize on the project's outcomes.

Circular Agronomics (final), Sep 2018 – Feb 2023

The Circular Agronomics (CA) project seeks to enhance Carbon (C), Nitrogen (N), and Phosphorus (P) cycling in European agro-ecosystems. Through diverse case studies, it aims to integrate agriculture into a circular economy, addressing environmental challenges such as emissions and water eutrophication. The project aims to improve resource efficiency, close loops in cropland farming, and contribute evidence-based recommendations for European Agricultural Policies, fostering sustainable and resilient economies in alignment with circular and zero-waste principles.

Presence of business models/outcomes in the market among Key Exploitable Results

This project emphasizes comprehensive market analyses and business model developments. A strategic action plan for commercialization includes assessing company resources, competitive advantages, financial projections, and a commercialization roadmap. It involves a thorough understanding of market trends, customer segments, and competitors, which can be instrumental for FoodCLIC in formulating a market entry strategy.

Climefish (final), Apr 2016 – Mar 2020

ClimeFish aims to strategically enhance sustainable seafood production by identifying climate-compatible areas and species. Employing biological models and forecasting, the project evaluates production scenarios, guiding socio-economic analyses for risk and opportunity assessment. Collaboration with stakeholders informs the development of climate-enabled management plans for three production sectors, addressing potential impacts of three climate scenarios. The ClimeFish Decision Support Framework facilitates comprehensive analysis and visualization, with international stakeholder involvement ensuring lasting impact post-project.

Presence of business models/outcomes in the market among Key Exploitable Results

Climefish introduces an innovative approach by focusing on the exploitation of a Decision Support System, tailored to the market needs. This project could offer valuable insights into leveraging technological tools for market advantage in FoodCLIC.

SEAFOODTOMORROW (final), Nov 2017 – Apr 2021

The SEAFOODTOMORROW project, addresses the urgent challenge of ensuring socio-economic and environmental sustainability in seafood production and processing. With a consortium of 19 leading research organizations and industry experts, the project aims to validate and optimize commercial solutions. Focusing on safety assessments through enhanced sensors and biosensors,

SEAFOODTOMORROW seeks to establish a robust quality control framework, fostering confidence in seafood products. The project also strives to enhance user acceptance, visibility, and market scalability, ultimately improving the availability of healthier seafood options.

Proposal of innovative exploitation tools

This project utilizes a range of dissemination mechanisms, including e-newsletters, workshops, stakeholder events, and a comprehensive communication campaign. While it lacks in employing more contemporary tools like hackathons, its extensive reach includes various stakeholder groups, from the scientific community to policy makers.

An interesting way to classify the project's Key Exploitable Results is the sheet presented in Appendix of SEAFOODTOMORROW's Exploitation Plan – the Horizon Results Platform (HRP) Template - which offers a deep insight into results allowing to share multimedia contents such as videos, images, links.

Links with other European projects

SEAFOODTOMORROW has established effective connections with projects like AQUAEXCEL2020 and SIMBA, facilitating complementarity and avoiding overlap.

Pro-enrich (final), May 2018 – Oct 2021

The EU-funded Pro-Enrich project responds to the increasing global demand for alternative protein sources and phenolic products. Targeting traditional agricultural residues like rapeseed meal, olives, tomatoes, and citrus fruits, previously considered waste, the project aims to convert them into valuable resources for various applications such as food ingredients, pet food, cosmetics, and adhesives. With a collaborative effort involving 16 partners from 7 countries, spanning the entire biorefinery value chain, Pro-Enrich seeks to isolate and purify proteins, polyphenols, dietary fibres, and pigments, contributing to more sustainable and healthier choices in response to consumer preferences and environmental concerns.

Presence of business models/outcomes in the market among Key Exploitable Results

Pro-enrich provides a detailed analysis of marketable technologies based on Technology Readiness Level (TRL), scalability of processes, and target markets.

Proposal of innovative exploitation tools

The project emphasizes Intellectual Property Rights measures for each exploitable result and outlines clear exit strategies, including partnerships, upscaling, and market launch. Its structured approach to IP and market entry could be an interesting reference for FoodCLIC.

AUTHENT-NET (final), Apr 2016 – Mar 2018

AUTHENT-NET seeks to address the historical lack of consolidated anti-food fraud capabilities in Europe by mobilizing and coordinating national research funding bodies. The project, involving 19 participants from 10 Member States and the US, aims to coordinate interdisciplinary research efforts, evaluate existing national research, establish transnational mechanisms for information exchange, and develop a high-level strategy for transnational research on food authenticity. Anticipated impacts include improved coordination among research budget holders, enhanced awareness of existing research, a joint strategy for food fraud research and the capability to deliver

transnational European research on food fraud. The two-year project aims to strengthen collaboration and strategic planning to combat food fraud across Member States.

Presence of business models/outcomes in the market among Key Exploitable Results

AUTHENT-NET's deliverable focuses on providing a comprehensive list of member states' national status reports on food authenticity. This structured approach to collating and presenting market-oriented data could be a valuable model for FoodCLIC in understanding and navigating diverse market landscapes.

3.2 INSIGHTS

The comprehensive analysis of the selected Exploitation schemes underlines some interesting aspects which could be inspirational for enriching FoodCLIC's exploitation strategy, here synthesized:

- **Market Analysis and Business Model Synergy:** Utilize the insights from projects like Circular Agronomics and Pro-enrich to develop a nuanced understanding of market trends, customer segments, and competitive landscapes. This should be amalgamated with robust business model development, focusing on scalability, technological readiness, and market entry strategies.
- **Leveraging Technology for Market Advantages:** Inspired by Climefish, explore the use of advanced technological tools, such as decision support systems, to gain a competitive edge in the market.
- **Strategic Project Collaborations:** Encourage synergies with other relevant projects and initiatives, as seen in SEAFOODTOMORROW, to enhance resource utilization, avoid overlap, and foster complementarity.
- **Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) Measures:** Follow the approach demonstrated by Pro-enrich to protect intellectual property, vital for securing market positions and future commercial prospects.
- **Clear Exit Strategies:** Develop exit strategies encompassing partnerships, upscaling, and market launch, ensuring a sustainable transition from project results to marketable products.

In the comprehensive analysis conducted on the exploitation schemes of various European food-related projects, a notable observation is the absence of considerations for incorporating impact finance tools to bolster the exploitation of project outcomes. Impact finance, encompassing various financial instruments designed to generate positive societal and environmental effects alongside financial returns, has not emerged as a prominent feature in the strategic planning of these initiatives. However, in the subsequent paragraph, we will elaborate on the concept of impact finance tools and elucidate how these mechanisms can be strategically employed to advance projects with a pronounced societal impact, using the FoodCLIC initiative as a case in point.

4. FOCUS ON INVESTMENTS SCHEMES: IMPACT FINANCE AS INSTRUMENT TO SUPPORT OUTCOME-BASED PROJECTS

4.1 WHY FINANCE FOR IMPACT? THE NEED FOR NEW FINANCIAL MODELS

The global financial crisis started in August 2007 highlighted the need to rediscover a more human and equitable dimension of economic and financial systems, after decades of inadequate market discipline (Chapra, 2014), as well as for financial models able to allocate funds to its most productive use (Schoenmaker, 2017).

Another relevant challenge of recent years concerns the access to finance by individuals and companies (Kim and Hann, 2019). Regarding the advancement of new financial models, the need for greater inclusion of people and small businesses that would not normally have the characteristics to access financial services is vital. (Collins et al., 2013; Zhang et al., 2016).

The market has started to realise how shareholder wealth maximization is no longer a valid guide to the creation of sustainable wealth (Fatemi and Fooladi, 2013). A paradigm shift has become more than necessary and, consequently, various models of sustainable finance have emerged. As a matter of fact, one of the main changes we have witnessed in recent years is the penetration of moral and ethical considerations into financial mechanisms, and thus attention to environmental, social and governance (ESG) aspects. This vision differs from traditional finance, which focuses solely on financial return and risk (Schoenmaker, 2017).

Besides the bottom-up market-based influences on the financial system, a top-down institutions-based force is additionally fostering the adoption of sustainable finance solutions. As the spread of environmental, social and governance aspects generated positive feedback from the markets and customers, the jump on the sustainability bandwagon required more strict regulations and boundaries that avoid potentially misleading behaviour (e.g., green washing and social washing). For these reasons, countries started to cooperate for a more regulated financial system especially with respect to the disclosure of sustainability and impact.

These emerging approaches in the financial sector are presented and discussed in this chapter. We identify four main categories of new financial models.

Disintermediation	Long-term risk protection	Value alignment	Solving social and environmental problems
Alternative finance	Responsible finance	Islamic finance	Microfinance
		Sustainable investing	Impact Finance

Figure 1: New models in finance

Disintermediation

Disintermediation refers to those financial models that bypass the need for the intermediation of financial institutions and rely on direct interaction and exchange between individuals without the need for “orthodox institutions” (ex. Banks) (Collins et al., 2013). Disintermediation is the result of increasing competition from other financial institutions different from banks as well as technological development. While financial sector organisations have acted as intermediaries in the financial system by providing an invaluable service to clients, their functions are now increasingly supplanted by new technology-driven business models. For instance, in the banking sector, online lending platforms allow individuals and businesses to lend and borrow between each other. Here we can find alternative finance that can operate through different types of financial instruments whose socio-economic foundation is built upon financial disintermediation.

Long-term risk protection

Holding long-term investments requires understanding, identifying and managing long-term financial risks and opportunities related to them. Investment institutions, in their asset allocation, portfolio construction and risk management processes and decisions, regularly and rigorously assess whether their investments are resilient and can be sustained indefinitely. Nowadays, it is widely acknowledged that Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) considerations can impact long-term risks and opportunities in financial markets. Under this section we will outline, under the label of *Responsible finance*, the integration of ESG criteria into financial analysis to protect a portfolio from operational or reputational risk. ESG investing considers a broader set of metrics to measure a company's risks which also assess how environmental, social and governance risk factors affect its performance, both positively and negatively.

Value alignment

Value-driven investing represent investments whose goals in defining the allocation strategy is to allocate financial resources to sectors and/or companies that can contribute to sustainable development at the same time ensure that the financial return is in line with market return standards.

This can happen in different ways:

- *Islamic finance*, which involves putting money in activities compliant with the investor’s religious values. One example that will be discussed is Islamic finance.
- *Sustainable investing*, which involves actively removing or choosing investments based on specific social or environmental guidelines.

Solving social and environmental problems

An ever-increasing number of mainstream investors are showing interest in allocating capital in a way that can contribute to addressing a wide array of societal issues. Under this section, we will outline the two models of impact finance and microfinance.

Differently from value driven investment and from mere philanthropy, *impact finance* is the purposeful allocation of financial resources to initiatives that can deliver measurable societal impact (social and environmental) alongside financial return in undercapitalized area (Geobey and Weber, 2013; Weber, 2016; Carè and Wendt, 2018). *Microfinance* has the specific objective of making the financial system more inclusive by providing loans and insurance products tailored for those clients usually excluded from the traditional financial system.

4.2 ALTERNATIVE FINANCE INSTRUMENTS

Alternative finance is an umbrella term that covers a range of very different models that aim to overcome the intermediation role of a financial institution (disintermediation), so that the funders and the fundraisers are directly connected (Allen et al., 2012). Thus, these financial models rely on direct interaction and exchange between individuals without the need for orthodox institutions (Collins et al., 2013). Alternative finance solutions link individuals who have extra funds to those who need them, working outside the conventional financial system (Baeck et al., 2014; Zhang et al., 2016). It is thus characterised by absence of lengthy application forms, low documentation, almost no collateral and/or minimum credit score requirements, high approval rates, and fast funding, even for cash flow and asset finance needs. Overall, alternative finance aims to give “individuals more control over their money as well as new outlets to invest or donate it” (p.7, Nesta, 2014).

Figure 2 provides many examples of alternative finance models that can be sum up in three groups: people lending money to each other or to businesses; people donating to community projects; and businesses trading their invoices (Nesta, 2014).

	Alternative Finance Model	Definition
Investment-based Models	Marketplace/P2P Consumer Lending	Individuals or institutional funders provide a loan to a consumer borrower.
	Balance Sheet Consumer Lending	The platform entity provides a loan directly to a consumer borrower.
	Marketplace/P2P Business Lending	Individuals or institutional funders provide a loan to a business borrower.
	Balance Sheet Business Lending	The platform entity provides a loan directly to a business borrower.
	Marketplace/P2P Property Lending	Individuals or institutional funders provide a loan secured against a property to a consumer or business borrower.
	Real Estate Crowdfunding	Individuals or institutional funders provide equity or subordinated-debt financing for real estate.
	Equity-based Crowdfunding	Individuals or institutional funders purchase equity issued by a company.
	Other	We include two additional categories, which are not presented individually due to small sample size. They are Revenue-sharing/Profit-Sharing ³ , and Debt-based Securities/Debentures. ⁴
Non-investment-based models	Reward-based Crowdfunding	Backers provide funding to individuals, projects or companies in exchange for non-monetary rewards or products.
	Donation-based Crowdfunding	Donors provide funding to individuals, projects or companies based on philanthropic or civic motivations with no expectation of monetary or material return.

Figure 2: A Taxonomy of Alternative Finance Models (Source: Ziegler et al. 2018)

The alternative finance market is relatively diverse, we will focus here on three specific models: crowdfunding peer-to-peer lending and balance sheet lending.

Crowdfunding

Crowdfunding is a novel method for funding a variety of new projects, allowing founders to request funding from many individuals, the “crowd”, often in return for future products or equity. This is usually done via or with the help of the Internet. Individual projects and businesses are financed with small contributions from a large number of individuals, “allowing innovators, entrepreneurs and business owners to utilise their networks to raise capital.” (De Buysere et al., 2012)

In 2021, the global crowdfunding market was valued at 12.27 billion U.S. dollars and was forecast to double by 2027, growing at compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 11 percent.² Over the years, a better regulatory environment and a greater professionalization of insiders have allowed a strong

² Global Crowdfunding Market Size, Status and Forecast 2020-2027

but healthy growth in the sector. In fact, from 2015 to 2020 the sector has recorded promising results both in terms of capital raised and number of supporters and investors who first approached aimed at this digital financing tool. From 2015 to 2020 the crowdfunding platforms in Italy raised a total of € 778,813,773².

There are four models of crowdfunding:

- *Equity crowdfunding*, which addresses early-stage unlisted company (a company that is not listed on a stock market) in exchange for shares in that company. The crowdfunding platforms allow the project to collect financing shares, even small ones, from a large number of subjects.
 - *Donation crowdfunding* or *donation-based crowdfunding* in which the crowd donates to project with a social purpose or a charity, without expecting the funds to be returned.
 - *Rewards-based crowdfunding*, in which individuals donate to a project or business with the expectation of receiving a non-financial reward in return, such as goods or services at a later stage (e.g., a unique service or a new product, pre-selling). This form of crowdfunding allows companies to launch with orders already on the books and cash-flow secured (a major issue for new businesses) and gathers an audience before a product launch.
 - *Real Estate crowdfunding* in which fintech logic are applied to capital collection for Real Estate investments and the capital raised is used to purchase, develop, or refurbish a Real Estate asset with the aim of subsequent use or transaction.
- Examples of crowdfunding platforms are Kickstarter at a global level and Lita.co in Italy.

Peer-to-peer lending

Peer-to-peer (P2P) lending (sometimes called crowdlending) is a direct alternative to a bank loan with the difference that, instead of borrowing from a single source, companies can borrow directly from tens, sometimes hundreds, of individuals who are willing to lend. Crowd lenders often bid for loans by offering an interest rate at which they would lend. Borrowers then accept loan offers at the lowest interest rate. Internet-based platforms are used to match lenders with borrowers. Due diligence is carried out for each loan request, as crowdfunding platforms have a duty to protect both businesses and investor interests. Platforms normally require financial accounts and a trading track record.

- Examples of P2P lending is Lending Club at a global level, and Smartika in Italy.

Balance sheet lending

Also referred to as portfolio lending, balance sheet lending involves a monetary loan in which the original lender retains the debt throughout the life cycle of the loan. In balance sheet lending (also called portfolio lending), the platform provides a loan directly to a consumer (Balance sheet consumer lending) or business (Balance sheet business lending) borrower. The main difference between traditional P2P lending and balance sheet lending is how the risk is structured if a loan goes

bad. In P2P lending, the platform does not lend to the borrower but merely link borrowers with investors between who the loan agreement is made. Conversely, in balance sheet lending the P2P platform (or another type of balance sheet lender) assumes the risk, becoming directly liable for any losses. Balance sheet lending can take many different forms, but the common trait is that the platform provides loans on their own risk.

4.3 BLENDED FINANCE

Blended finance is the use of catalytic capital from public or philanthropic sources to increase private sector investment in developing countries and sustainable development. The most outstanding definition of blended finance is provided by The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). They define blended finance as:

*"Blended finance involves the strategic use of development finance and philanthropic funds to mobilize private capital flows to emerging and frontier markets. It represents a promising approach to financing sustainable development in developing countries and is recognized as an important tool in the financing for development toolbox. At its core, blended finance aims to de-risk investments and make projects more attractive to private investors by blending concessional public or philanthropic resources (such as grants, concessional loans, or guarantees) with private capital."*³

This definition emphasizes the strategic combination of different sources of funding to catalyze investments that contribute to sustainable development goals in **developing countries**. The primary objective is to combine concessional (subsidized or low interest) funds with commercial capital public and philanthropic resources alongside private sector investments to address financing gaps, reduce risks, and encourage the flow of capital toward impactful projects in sectors like infrastructure, healthcare, education, and renewable energy.

This approach aims to address societal challenges by leveraging different types of funding, such as grants, concessional loans, equity, and commercial financing, to create more attractive and viable investment opportunities. Blended finance mechanisms often target sectors like infrastructure, renewable energy, healthcare, education, and agriculture to drive positive social and environmental impact alongside financial returns.

Blended finance is a versatile tool that plays a crucial role in catalyzing investment in areas that face challenges in attracting traditional sources of financing. To distinguish blended finance, we can rely on the following key elements:

- *Risk Mitigation*: one of the primary objectives of blended finance is to mitigate risks associated with investing in projects or regions perceived as high-risk. By combining different sources of funding, it becomes possible to allocate risks strategically, making investments more appealing to private investors who might otherwise be deterred by uncertainties or perceived vulnerabilities. By reducing the upfront risks and increasing the

³ <https://www.oecd.org/dac/financing-sustainable-development/blended-finance-principles/>

overall financial viability of projects, blended finance encourages private investors to participate in ventures that align with sustainable development objectives.

- *Focus on Impactful Sectors*: blended finance often targets sectors critical for sustainable development, such as infrastructure, renewable energy, healthcare, education, and agriculture.
- *Multiple Stakeholder Collaboration*: it involves collaboration among various stakeholders, including governments, multilateral development banks, philanthropic organizations, impact investors, and private sector entities. Each party brings its expertise, resources, and networks to create investment structures that are both financially viable and socially impactful.
- *Tailored Financing Structures*: blended finance utilizes diverse financial instruments and structures, such as concessional loans, guarantees, equity investments, and technical assistance. These structures are tailored to meet the specific needs of a project or investment, ensuring that it aligns with both financial and impact objectives.
- *Measurement and Reporting Impact*: There is an emphasis on measuring and reporting the impact of blended finance initiatives. Metrics related to social, environmental, and economic outcomes are tracked and evaluated to ensure transparency, accountability, and effectiveness in achieving sustainable development goals.

Blended finance employs a variety of financial instruments and mechanisms to combine different types of capital effectively. Some commonly used instruments include:

- *Grants*: these are funds provided by governments, foundations, or international organizations that do not need to be repaid. Grants are often used to reduce the risk for other investors or to finance specific developmental or social impact components of a project.
- *Concessional Loans*: these loans offer more favourable terms than traditional commercial loans, such as lower interest rates, longer grace periods, or extended repayment schedules. They help to make projects financially viable and attractive to private investors.
- *Equity Investments*: investing in a project or enterprise by purchasing ownership shares provides a stake in the business's success. Equity investments can offer higher potential returns but also involve higher risks compared to debt instruments.
- *Guarantees*: guarantees act as a form of insurance against potential losses for investors or lenders in case of default or certain predefined risks. They can encourage private sector participation by mitigating perceived risks.
- *Blended Funds*: these are investment vehicles that pool together different types of capital (grants, concessional finance, and commercial funds) to support projects or enterprises aligned with sustainable development goals.
- *Technical Assistance*: funding and support for capacity building, training, knowledge transfer, or other forms of assistance to enhance the success and impact of projects. Technical assistance helps to improve the operational and managerial aspects of initiatives.
- *Impact Investment Vehicles*: as detailed in the following section including social impact bonds and sustainability linked bonds.

These instruments are often combined in different ways to create customized financial structures tailored to the specific needs of projects or initiatives. The goal is to optimize risk-adjusted returns for investors while ensuring the achievement of social, environmental, and developmental objectives. By combining resources and expertise from different sectors, blended finance endeavours to create a more sustainable and inclusive approach to financing development projects.

Using Blended Finance to Mobilize Capital for Agricultural Development

When considering the use of blended finance concerning the agri-food domain, the main focus is on supporting small farmers in developing countries. Blended finance can enable Agri-SMEs to access more capital and targeted financial products to grow their businesses and their contribution to sustainable development. Different blended finance instruments can facilitate the mobilisation of commercial finance for agri-SMEs in different contexts, and risk mitigation instruments often hold particular potential, given that credit risk is often a key obstacle to financing this market segment. Moreover, blended finance models can promote financial inclusion by facilitating lending to specific projects, including those led by women and youth entrepreneurs. These initiatives aim to bridge the financing gap for underserved segments of the agricultural market.

Other relevant benefit of using blended finance in the agriculture are:

- *Stimulating New Markets:* Blended finance, especially through the provision of technical assistance and grants, can stimulate the creation of new markets and value chains centered around agri-SMEs. This can lead to innovative business models and economic development.
- *Flexibility and Innovation:* Blended finance programs should be designed to allow experimentation, innovation, and adjustments. Close consultation with target groups helps identify both supply and demand challenges associated with commercial finance.

The main models employed in blended finance to support the development of AGRI-SMEs are:

- *Global Agriculture and Food Security Program (GAFSP):* GAFSP is a multilateral mechanism that utilizes blended finance to address food security issues by providing financing to support agricultural productivity. It combines public and private funds to invest in projects focused on smallholder farmers in developing countries, aiming to improve their productivity and access to markets.
- *Agricultural Value Chain Financing:* Many financial institutions, supported by development finance institutions and impact investors, use blended finance models to provide financing along agricultural value chains. This involves funding various stages of the food production process, from farming inputs to processing, storage, and distribution, thereby enhancing efficiency and reducing post-harvest losses.
- *African Agriculture Trade and Investment Fund (AATIF):* AATIF is a fund that uses blended finance to invest in African agriculture and agribusinesses. It's supported by public and private investors, including development finance institutions, and aims to promote sustainable agriculture, food security, and economic development across the African continent.
- *Forest and Farm Facility (FFF):* FAO, in collaboration with the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) and other partners, established FFF. This initiative focuses on supporting forest and farm producer organizations in developing countries. It utilizes blended finance by combining funds from governments, international organizations, and private sector entities to promote sustainable forest management and increase the income and resilience of small-scale farmers.

The examples of blended finance worldwide are numerous. Without pretending to be exhaustive, in table 1, few examples are enlisted for illustrative purposes.⁴

Table 1: examples of blended finance worldwide

Nome of the project	Country	Providers of Finance and Technical Assistance	Financing Structure and Instruments Used	Focus
<i>Financing Ghanaian Agriculture (FinGAP)</i>	Ghana	USAID, Palladium	Payment by Result (PBR) Guarantees, Technical Assistance (TA)	Stimulating commercial lending to agribusiness and smallholder maize, rice, and soy farmers in rural Ghana through grants in the form of pay-for-result incentive schemes for financial institutions and business development services, as well as guarantees
<i>Programme for Rural Outreach of Financial Innovations and Technologies (PROFIT)</i>	Kenya	IFC, Agricultural Finance Corporation of Kenya	Credit Lines, Guarantees, Technical Assistance (TA)	Incentivizing commercial and microfinance banks to increase agricultural lending, diversify services to rural areas, and focus on innovation to reduce service costs for producer groups.
<i>Private Agriculture Sector Support (PASS)</i>	Tanzania	DANIDA, SIDA, Tanzanian Government, Agriculture Sector Programme Support (ASPS)	Guarantees, Technical Assistance (TA)	Providing guarantee schemes to encourage lending to specific targeted projects, such as women-owned and youth-led enterprises or initiatives
<i>Blending Happiness, Hazelnuts, and Finance in Bhutan</i>	Mountain Hazelnuts	ADB, IFC, Private Sector Window of GAFSP	Equity, Quasi-equity	Blended investment in creating a new market for hazelnut production in Bhutan by training farmers, facilitating access to markets, and using degraded land.
<i>Development of a Macauba-Based Silvopastoral System and Value Chain Implemented by Inocas</i>	Brazil	IDB, Forest Investment Programme, Althelia	Grant, Equity, Technical Assistance (TA)	Building a new commercial value chain for growing a native palm tree called Macauba in Brazil.
<i>Social Trust Fund to Incorporate Vulnerable Smallholder Farmers into Paragua's Chamomile Value Chain</i>	Paraguay	Government of Paraguay, Fundación Capital, Private Investors	Grants	Incorporating vulnerable smallholder farmers into the chamomile value chain through de-risking investments into product

⁴ OECD (2021) "Good blended finance practices can scale up finance for agri-SMEs", OECD Development Co-operation Directorate, Paris.

<i>Sustainable Landscapes Portfolio Guarantee, India</i>	<i>India</i>	USAID, Rabobank Foundation	Guarantees	Enabling lending by local partner financial institutions to SMEs, co-operatives, producer companies, and microfinance institutions engaged in sustainable landscape investments.
<i>Family Farming Financing Programme (PROAF), Mexico</i>	<i>Mexico</i>	Mexican Agriculture Development Bank (FIRA)	Guarantees, Technical Assistance (TA)	Stimulating commercial loans from co-operatives to family farmers combined with technical assistance from the public development finance institution FIRA.

As for the areas involved the project, one of the most active countries is the Netherlands, which is known for its advanced agricultural practices and expertise in agri-food innovations.

There are several initiatives and projects related to blended finance in the food and agriculture sector:

- *FoodStars Initiative*: The FoodStars Initiative, supported by the Dutch government and private sector partners, aims to enhance food security and agricultural productivity in developing countries. It combines public funds with private investments to support agribusinesses and smallholder farmers by providing access to finance, knowledge, and technology. The initiative focuses on sustainable agriculture practices and improving market access for small-scale producers.
- *FMO's Agribusiness Fund*: FMO, the Dutch development bank, operates an agribusiness fund that invests in agricultural enterprises in emerging markets. This fund combines public and private investments to support projects that promote sustainable agricultural practices, enhance food security, and empower local farming communities. It provides capital, technical assistance, and expertise to agribusinesses along the value chain.
- *Rabobank's Partnerships*: Rabobank, a leading Dutch cooperative bank specializing in agriculture and food financing, has been involved in various blended finance partnerships. It collaborates with international organizations, governments, and impact investors to support initiatives focused on sustainable agriculture, food security, and rural development. These partnerships often combine concessional funding with private investments to address challenges faced by farmers and food producers.
- *Dutch Good Growth Fund (DGGF)*: The DGGF, managed by the Netherlands Enterprise Agency (RVO), supports entrepreneurship and investments in developing countries, including those in the agriculture and food sectors. It provides a mix of finance, guarantees, and technical assistance to stimulate private sector investments and local economic development, often incorporating blended finance principles to maximize impact.

4.3 IMPACT FINANCE

The context in which financial instruments extract value from ESG criteria is impact finance. Impact finance adopts a social impact investing approach and refers to the deployment of financial resources primarily for social and environmental returns, as well as in some cases, a financial return (Nicholls, 2014). This approach explicitly aims to orient resources toward solutions to social or environmental challenges. The emergence of impact finance was boosted by two main factors:

- 1) The skepticism about the long-term sustainability and impact of traditional charitable models paired with the increased dissatisfaction with gaps and inefficiency in public services funding.
- 2) The requests from markets and institutions to evolve the ESG criteria from an aseptic measure of performance typical of responsible and sustainable investing, to a central condition for the selection of investment opportunities.

In this scenario, the role of impact finance emerged as that of a new financial model able to pursue higher effectiveness at societal level in capital allocation by leveraging decentralized mechanisms. This is linked particularly to the ability of social ventures to develop innovative solutions to neglected societal problems.

Figure 3: The finance spectrum

Definition, key characteristics, and rationale

Impact finance is defined as the purposeful allocation of financial resources to initiatives that can deliver measurable societal impact (social and environmental) alongside financial return in the undercapitalized area. The pillars that help to distinguish impact finance from all the other approaches are:

- *Intentionality*: the social impact is targeted intentionally, and the investment is explicitly made to achieve a positive benefit for the society. This means an explicit statement “ex-ante” and a proactive search of initiatives pursuing a social goal. The social impact is not an incidental side effect. (Addis et al. 2013; Brown and Swersky, 2012)
- *Measurability*: The social impact must be measurable and measured in a quantitatively and/or qualitatively way. The social goals, indeed, should be defined in an ex-ante phase and measured thanks to estimation, and verified ex-post the effective and efficient achievement of those impacts. (O’Donohoe et al., 2010; Wood et al., 2012)
- *Additionality*: The impact investments are done in undercapitalized areas, where the activities would have been excluded by any other investors and thus not implemented. (So and Staskevicius, 2015)

Impact finance is well identified by the principle of additionality since it is not intended to substitute other financial sources such as traditional philanthropy or public funding that have historically supported social sector’s initiatives, but to complement them. Impact finance, thus, operates in those areas or sectors that are not considered in charge of the public sector or the public sector has not enough funding to intervene; or in those undercapitalized areas because they are not attractive for traditional investors. In this sense, impact finance has the role to target neglected areas of social services and thus complementing sources of funding traditionally devoted to providing services to the society. Rather, this approach seeks novel forms of funding and various combinations of risk and return to achieve social aims.

In more operative terms, impact finance adds a third criterion, on the top of risk and return, in the investment strategy: social impact as shown. This means that impact investor must also consider the impact return and the impact risk, on the top of the financial ones, and should try to optimize all together.

According to Hornsby and Blumberg (2013), to select investments the investor should look at four different parameters: financial return, financial risk, impact return and impact risk. Financial returns in impact investments may be above, equal to, or below market rates with a minimum of capital preservation (Grabenwarter and Liechtenstein, 2011; Evenett and Richter 2011; Best and Harji 2013; Hochstadter and Scheck, 2015). Impact return refers to how much social and environmental outcomes for society are fulfilled thanks to investment actions (Emerson and Freundlich, 2012; Reeder and Colantonio, 2013). It is important to articulate at the outset the desired impact according to the context of the investment field chosen (Brandstetter and Lehner, 2015). Here, the problem for impact investors is the lack of methodologies for measuring it that have become the market

standards (Grabenwarter, 2013; Saltuk et al., 2013). In impact finance, the impact appraisal should be carried out at the pre-investment stage and post-investment stage,

Likely, the definition and calculation of impact risk have been only marginally investigated by scholars and practitioners (Brandstetter and Lehner, 2015; Fullwiler, 2016). The most diffuse definitions of impact risk consider it as:

- The risk of not generating the intended and stated social impact due to unpredictable events;
- The risk of not generating the level of social impact targeted/promised, so a measure of the certainty that an organization will deliver on its proposed impact;
- The risk of generating negative impact;
- The inability of properly measured/assessed the social return/social impact that leads to a lack of evidence;
- The probability of mission drift by the investor and the investees from social mission or financial mission.

The use of financial products for impact investing purposes involves the application of a Theory of Change (ToC) for investment opportunities. The measurement of social impact through a ToC approach defines the social and/or environmental problem that a financial product aims to solve, and the context in which it is supposed to be enacted. Thus, the identification of a precise impact objectives makes the ToC suitable for funds to operate in these contexts.

The pursuit of financial returns is a hallmark characteristic of impact investing, and these can widely vary from deeply concessionary to competitively market-rate. This year, just over two-thirds of respondents principally target risk-adjusted, market-rate returns, while the remaining third are split closely between below-market-rate: closer to market-rate (18%), and below-market-rate: closer to capital preservation.

Europe

European impact investments are growing. The EVPA study *“Accelerating Impact”*⁵ estimates the European direct impact investment market – i.e. investments directly made into enterprises addressing social and environmental challenges – at € 80 billion. European impact investment assets under management grew by a substantial 26% from 2020 to 2021, but still represent only 0.5% of the European mainstream investment market. The top areas covered – decent work and economic growth, reduced inequalities and climate action – include a mix of social and environmental goals, which shows how impact investors represent a force for change on both impact categories.

Looking at the sources of funding for impact investment, more than a quarter comes from individual investors. This trend is driven by countries with favourable regulations, which have proven to democratise access to impact investment and mobilise significant resources from retail investors, who are increasingly demanding sustainable and impact opportunities. This indicates that policy makers – both national and European – have a key role to play in making access to funding for retail

⁵ <https://www.evpa.ngo/insights/accelerating-impact>

investors easier. At the low end of the spectrum, foundations' endowment assets and high net worth individuals represent an untapped potential of resources which could be mobilised to support impact funds. EU funding accounts for 5% of the funding available to impact investors. This is heading in a positive direction, growing from 1% in 2020, and reflects the increased engagement of the European Investment Fund to deploy EU funds into public-private co-investments.

Instruments

Impact finance instruments can be clustered into three main groups: equity-based, debt-based, Public-Private Partnership.

Table 2: Types of impact finance instruments

	Equity-based	Debt-based	Public-Private Partnership for impact
Social ventures	Social impact fund <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Venture philanthropy 	Social impact loan	Payment by results Social Impact Bonds <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Outcome fund
Social infrastructures ⁶	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social impact fund 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social impact loan 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Payment by results

In the table above the different types of instruments are related to a different type of target: Social ventures and Social Infrastructures.

⁶ Social infrastructure can be defined as the construction and maintenance of facilities that support social services. Types of social infrastructure include healthcare (hospitals), education (schools and universities), public facilities (community housing and prisons) and transportation (railways and roads). All of these structures serve as the backbone for communities and societies.

Figure 4: representation of type of finance instruments

Equity based

The term equity refers to an investment, in the form of risk capital, in companies and organizations with the aim of generating a measurable social impact together with a financial return. Social impact equity is substantially comparable to traditional equity investments. The return can be realized when the shares are sold. It is not repayable, and the capital provider has several benefits like voting rights even if it is a more risky approach. In general, the equity investment is made in the risk capital of unlisted companies with high development potential in terms of products or services, new technologies and new market concepts whose risky nature would be compensated, in traditional finance, by high returns. However, social impact equity typically has lower expectations of return or, more precisely, it provides a primary importance to supporting innovative solutions to social problems and, therefore, they are prone, given a certain level of risk, to forgive a part of the financial return to get the social return.

The main difference between the social impact equity and traditional equity investments are:

- The impact nature of the objectives pursued by the invested companies.
- The type of agreements that define their governance structure within the invested companies.
- The so called “mission lock” obligations. They are legal constraints such as the obligation to reinvest a part of the profits of the investee company in other impact instruments or other strategies aimed at “blocking” the possibility that new shareholders of the company may take control and establish new lines of address.
- Sometimes the remuneration of the investors is “capped” to some extent in accordance with the statute or law, as in the case of specific forms of social entrepreneurship.

Examples of equity-based instrument of impact finance are social impact funds and Venture Philanthropy.

Social Impact Funds are a ready-to-deploy pool of capital available to social enterprises through a professionally managed, diversified fund. Professionals who manage the Social Impact Fund aim to establish lasting relationships with their investees and implement a multi-stage selection process before investing in an organization. They typically evaluate the social entrepreneur, the business idea and the social goal and the financial return (Achleitner and Heister, 2009; Miller and Wesley, 2010). First, they evaluate the company's social mission and found it to be a relevant predictive factor of efficiency. Enthusiasm for social change is considered an important trait because it is the source of the drive to achieve the enterprise's goals. Parameters which are often considered in the conventional business market are also evaluated, such as economic sustainability. Moreover, the passion of the social entrepreneur, its network, its reputation, and the management experience are considered relevant. The entrepreneurs' educational prestige as well as the performance measurement methodology, conceived as the ability to show results in a rigorous and accurate manner are important.

➤ Examples: SEFEA IMPACT, Oltre Venture, Phitrust.

Venture Philanthropy is a new approach to grant making which uses the tools and criteria of traditional venture funding. Venture Philanthropy is a high-engagement and long-term approach whereby an investor for impact supports a social purpose organisation to help it maximise its social impact (EVPA, 2004). Investors for impact can be highly engaged grant-makers or social investors (e.g., foundations, social impact funds). They are willing to take risks that most other investors are not prepared to take to support innovative solutions. Grossman and colleagues (2013) emphasize the approach to organizational building, and indeed venture philanthropists act as partners and in conjunction with financial support, they provide expertise and advice, focus on organizational development and on performance and impact assessment. EVPA (2006) identifies the following as some of the key elements of venture philanthropy:

- *High engagement:* venture philanthropists have a close hands-on relationship with the social entrepreneurs and ventures they support, driving innovative and scalable models of social change. Some may take board places on these organisations, and all are far more intimately involved at strategic and operational levels than are traditional non-profit funders.
- *Tailored financing:* as in venture capital, venture philanthropists take an investment approach to determine the most appropriate financing for each organisation. Depending on their own missions and the ventures they choose to support, venture philanthropists can operate across the spectrum of investment returns. Some offer nonreturnable grants (and thus accept a purely social return), while others use loan, mezzanine, or quasi-equity finance (thus blending risk-adjusted financial and social returns).
- *Multi-year support:* venture philanthropists provide substantial and sustained financial support to a limited number of organisations. Support typically lasts at least three-to-five years, with an objective of helping the organisation to become financially self-sustaining by the end of the funding period.

- *Non-financial support*: in addition to financial support, venture philanthropists provide value-added services such as strategic planning, marketing and communications, executive coaching, human resource advice and access to other networks and potential funders.
- *Organisational capacity-building*: venture philanthropists focus on building the operational capacity and long-term viability of the organisations in their portfolios, rather than funding individual projects or programmes. They recognize the importance of funding core operating costs to help these organisations achieve greater social impact and operational efficiency.
- *Performance measurement*: venture philanthropy investment is performance based, placing emphasis on good business planning, measurable outcomes, achievement of milestones, and high levels of financial accountability and management competence.

Debt based

Debt-based impact finance models are mainly provided for long-term projects with stable and predictable cash flows for a mature business model and stable cash flows. Social impact debt instruments consist of bonds or loans issued by a heterogeneous group of lenders and, as in traditional finance, assume that a company finances its business through borrowed capital. The money received must be repaid according to a series of rules that typically establish, for example, the duration of the investment period and the interest rate granted to the investor. Debt capital is repayable at the end of the period and the investee has to pay an interest payment in certain pre-defined time intervals. Compared to equity-based instruments, debt-based ones are safer models of capital provision with a lower-risk. Fedele and Miniaci (2010) found that social impact organizations are more interested in these forms of financial models. Indeed, private debt seems to be particularly adequate to give rise to entrepreneurial growth programs, and, compared to equity instruments, it allows a greater degree of autonomy of companies.

One example of debt-based instrument is the *Social Impact Loans*. Social banks provide loans to create a social and/or environmental benefits. All their products and services focus exclusively on creating and sustaining social value through financial products and services. It is an unsecured medium- or loan-long term aimed at companies that wish to finance a project that pursues a social goal intentional, positive, and measurable. However, this type of instrument presents some open issues:

- *Credit scoring*: a credit scoring tool that correlates the level of risk and social impact of potential clients has not yet been developed.
- *Identification of social entrepreneurship*: it is still difficult for social banking to identify potential social businesses to support through loans.
- *Social impact measurement*: banks are still not implementing standard impact measurement tools to assess the social impact of their client.

On September 2019 the UNEP Finance Initiative together with 30 international banks have launched the Principles for Responsible Banking. The principles, that have been signed from more than 170 institutions have the goals to align the financial operations of credit institutions to the SDGs framework and the Paris Agreement declarations. The six principles are coupled with a practical guide for their implementation and a four-year plan to be implemented from the signatories.

- Examples: Social Impact Banking, Triodos Bank, Big Society Capital.

Public-private partnership for impact

Public-private partnerships (PPPs) for impact are financial instruments that entail a partnership between an agency of the government or a public administration and the private sector in the delivery of financial support and capital provision to a social initiative or to a social impact organization. More in depth, PPPs for impact are characterized by a plurality of organizational forms, all of which differ based on the degree of hybridization of resources between public and private actors (George *et al.*, 2023). Such degrees of hybridization can depend on the contracts stipulated between public and private parties, paving the way for a wide range of project financing models underpinning such collaborations (Sinclair *et al.*, 2021). Among these, outcome-based incentives (OBI) have become at the forefront of financing models for PPPs, ensuring that financial rewards are tied to the specific performance outcomes (Bovaird & Davies, 2011; Albertson *et al.*, 2018). The success of PPPs relies on the long-term adherence to shared commitments by public and private actors (Forrer *et al.*, 2010). Contracts regulate PPPs and can rely on different financial instruments (George *et al.*, 2023). However, traditional input-based contracts are often criticized for lacking efficiency and accountability (Heinrich, 2002). The shift towards outcome-based models gained momentum as governments aimed to maximize value and maintain high service standards for citizens (Vecchi *et al.*, 2021). One of the earliest examples was the UK's Private Finance Initiative (PFI), which aimed to bridge infrastructure gaps by incorporating private sector expertise and capital (Kerr, 1998; UK House of Commons, 2003).

In this context, innovative forms of financial instruments that can manage contracts and PPPs to achieve grand challenges and, more broadly, to ensure public value generation are emerging (Vecchi *et al.*, 2022). OBI stem from this context. OBI defines those contractual agreements between public and private entities aimed at designing and delivering public service interventions, such as other outcome-based contracting (OBC) (Bovaird & Davies, 2011). Indeed, this innovative form has rapidly gained legitimacy in outsourcing public services following the rise of New Public Management (Osborne, 2016). OBI starts from the assumption that public services can be cost-efficient when delivered by private entities and ensure that the stakeholders' needs are better understood (Bovaird & Davies, 2011; Albertson *et al.*, 2018).

Moreover, OBCs represent a dynamic shift in how public-private partnerships (PPPs) are structured and executed, emphasizing results over inputs and activities (Albertson *et al.*, 2018). An OBC focuses on achieving specific, measurable outcomes, ensuring that the contracted services or projects generate the desired impact (Fitzgerald *et al.*, 2023). Unlike traditional contracts that outline the steps to be taken, OBCs stipulate the desired end-state and hold the private partner accountable for its achievement. Furthermore, OBCs function on the principle of aligning the interests of both the public and private sectors through shared goals. This alignment is achieved by meticulously defining the expected results and performance metrics (Albertson *et al.*, 2018). The private partner is then empowered to devise and implement strategies that best deliver those outcomes (Bovaird & Davies, 2011). OBCs encourage innovation and flexibility by concentrating on outcomes, enabling private partners to adapt their approaches based on evolving circumstances (Fitzgerald *et al.*, 2023). This

approach fosters competition and streamlines resource allocation and risk management, as the responsibility for performance rests with the entity best suited to manage it (Eneqvist *et al.*, 2022). More in-depth, compared to other forms of PPPs, such as Design-Build-Finance-Operate (DBFO) or Build-Operate-Transfer (BOT), OBCs stand out for their pronounced focus on outcomes. While DBFO and BOT models predominantly center around the private partner delivering a specific facility or service, OBCs diverge by mandating predefined achievements (World Bank, 2022; UNECE, 2008). This results-oriented approach compels the private sector to devise innovative solutions that meet contractual obligations and generate societal benefits (Fitzgerald *et al.*, 2023; Albertson *et al.*, 2018).

In the context of Outcome Based Incentives, we present here three types of these partnerships: Payment-by-results, Social Impact Bonds, Outcome funds.

Payment by results (PBR) is a new form of financing that makes payments contingent on the verification of results. Generally, it is a mechanism where all or part of the payment from the commissioning authority depends on the provider achieving outcomes specified by the commissioner. It is the founding principle of outcome-based bargaining, i.e., a public procurement management approach whereby the Public Administration commissions a private body to achieve specific objectives. The PBR principle establishes that the Public Administration is responsible for paying for the services provided only if the results have been achieved, to the extent and according to the conditions established at the time of the definition of the contract. Service providers therefore need to make an upfront investment, and some form of upfront payment or 'fee for service'. Providers are, to a greater or lesser extent, free to choose the interventions needed to secure the desired outcomes, and they are motivated to ensure successful performance. The deferral in payment generally is part of the attraction for commissioners but creates risk for providers who need to finance the upfront investment in the interim. There are reported instances of smaller welfare-to-work providers withdrawing from contracts due to this time lag between investment and payment. One approach to overcome this and to make the schemes more attractive to potential bidders, is to include a proportion of upfront payment that is not contingent on the achievement of a specified outcome. Payment by results has three key elements:

- Disbursements tied to the achievement of clearly specified results: payment for outcomes such as completion of education, rather than payment for inputs such as provision of textbooks.
- Recipient discretion – the recipient has space to decide how results are achieved; and
- Robust verification of results as the trigger for disbursement.

In *Social Impact Bond*, a separate private investor pays for the activities of a social service provider thereby taking the financial responsibility for tackling a social issue (see the figure below). For the commissioner, it is a means to harness private resources through joint delivery, especially attractive in the contexts of constrained public budgets. From the investor's point of view, it is not only a contribution to a social cause, but also a financial opportunity. For social service provider, SIB provides up-front capital, shifting the financial risk onto the investor. A SIB intervention aims at improving the situation of the target group, resulting at the same time (if the intervention is

successful) in government savings (e.g., unemployment benefits, if the target group is employed because of the intervention). An independent evaluator measures the target group outcomes periodically and reports on the SIBs progress and final results. The service provider can use the progress assessments to adapt and improve the intervention. Based on the SIBs final results, which are predefined in a contract signed by all stakeholders, the commissioner (government) pays part of its cost-savings to the investor, which should compensate for the upfront capital plus interest.

Figure 5: Basic social impact bonds model

Private funding for SIBs can be issued in two main ways: through SIB funds and the individual SIBs. The main difference is that SIBs funds issue multiple contracts focusing on the same social issue, whereas individual SIBs release one payment contract at a time. Furthermore, individual SIBs take one of the following forms:

- In a *direct SIB*, a delivery contract is signed between the outcomes-payer and service provider. The service provider carries the risk if results are not achieved, as the investor is lending funds and is repaid first with the loan secured against the enterprise's assets.
- *Intermediated SIBs* also involve an intermediary to liaise between investors, service providers and the commissioner. Social Finance, a multinational NGO mentioned above, is one of the most notable actors in this role in a number of countries. In an intermediated SIB, the delivery contract is signed between the outcomes payer and an investor-owned special purpose vehicle (SPV), which contracts the service provider, supports the performance management process, and refines the financial model. The risk is shared within the SPV among investors and the repayment depends on the SIB's structure.
- Finally, a *managed SIB* is signed between the outcomes-payer and the prime contractor (usually an intermediary), who usually manages the entire process. The investors carry

the risk but at the same time, they obtain gains if results are achieved or exceeded (OECD, 2016).

At least theoretically, SIBs offer opportunities to all the parties involved. The government shares the financial risk of resolving social issues to private investors. ‘No cure no pay’ ensures that governments only pay for proven results, which also clarifies the effectiveness of the intervention. Moreover, different government departments, agencies and arms can use this instrument to pool funds when interventions address issues that cut across different mandates, and to achieve outcomes of interest to more than one departmental sponsor. The instrument is not limited to annual budgets, so can be used for multi-year interventions, avoiding the need for repeated funding applications and decisions that also pose risk to intervention continuity (Marks and Weaver, 2017). Meanwhile, private investors get the chance to follow on their corporate social responsibility (CSR) and may obtain returns on social investments. Finally, the social service providers are offered a long-term investment that may be used to design, test and implement their innovative interventions on a larger scale – in other words, they are provided with better environment to scale-up.

Generally, SIB enthusiasts praise them for pulling together diverse actors and expertise from different domains, fostering cooperation and innovation, as well as promoting the culture of performance measurement. Therefore, this model is becoming increasingly popular across the world (see the figure below). For example, as of January 2020, Brookings Institution has mapped out a total of 176 impact bonds in 32 countries (Brookings, 2020)— marking around 24% increase in nine months (as in January Brookings found 134 SIBs in total (Global Economy and Development at Brookings, 2019)). Although most of them are in the UK, the US and generally high-income countries, the model is also emerging in the developing regions.

Nonetheless, SIBs are also often related in the literature to various risks, such as technical issues, considerable administrative burden and transactional costs (sometimes even overweighting the possible government savings), perverse incentives (“parking”, “creaming”, “cherry-picking”, etc.). Other critics emphasise the ideological shifts, shrinking role of the public sector in social protection, and that SIBs reduce the central feature of social intervention of providing support to a by-product of investment and turning citizens into commodities (Roy, McHugh, & Sinclair, 2018). During the Covid-19 crisis, social impact bonds gained momentum, due to a sudden increase in issuance driven by COVID-19. In April, \$12.7 billion worth of social impact bonds were issued around the world, more than the total amount raised in 2019.

Outcome bonds are a specific family of impact bonds, which are the Development Impact Bonds (DIB), expressly created for the developing countries. The core characteristics of the DIB are:

- Financing is provided to support a development programme.
- Money is provided by a private investor who earns a return if the program is successful.
- The outcomes to be measured are agreed upon the outset and independently verified.
- The main objective is to solve a local problem with an innovative solution.

An outcome fund is a funding mechanism that allows the creation and support of many outcome-based contracts in parallel, under a common structure. Outcomes funds’ primary goal is to improve

services and programs that address complex social issues by scaling up the contracting market based on outcomes. The aim of the Outcome Fund is to expand the use of outcome-based contracts to enable service providers to achieve social outcomes changes for particular target populations. They aim to contribute to more effective solutions for tackling complex social issues through greater collaboration and synergy between actors.

Outcomes funds may differ in many ways. However, we can highlight two key characteristics common to all Outcomes funds:

- Focus on outcomes – All Outcomes-fund share the desire to create better social outcomes. This indicates a transition of focus away from an activity-based approach and output-based approach to an outcome-based approach. This focus is linked to the creation of outcomes-based contracts for funding social projects.
- Welcome multiple outcomes-based contracts – Rather than funding and developing outcomes-based contracts one at a time, Outcomes-fund facilitate the funding and development of several of these projects, which sometimes could even be designed and/or implemented simultaneously. Even when the design/implementation of projects is sequential, the speed at which these projects are set up and launch could be significantly reduced by accessing standard procedures and design features.

Outcomes-fund vary considerably in their scale:

- The amount of money available for paying for outcomes.
- The number of outcomes-based contracts funded.
- The number of different actors contributing to the fund.
- The time frame allocated, population, policy theme and geography to be targeted also vary.

A simplified operational process for Outcomes fund follows four key stages:

1. *Outcomes funding is designated:* One or several actors (public, private and/or philanthropic) allocate capital to the operation of an Outcomes-fund. This is money that will be mainly used to pay for social outcomes, allowing funders to act as outcomes payers.
2. *Call for outcomes-based project proposals:* A partnership comprised by actors such as service provider(s), social investor(s) and/or intermediary(s) apply to the available funding with proposals for social projects based on outcomes.
3. *Selection of successful projects:* The fund selects proposals which become outcomes contracts to be implemented.
4. *Payment conditional on measurable social outcomes:* If social outcomes are achieved through the proposed service, contractors receive payment based on the specified outcome. To do so, a process of outcomes validation is set, based on administrative data or other evaluation methods. There are different approaches for defining the payment for outcomes achieved, such as the rate card approach, which provides a menu of highly specified outcomes each with specific maximum prices attached by the outcomes fund administrator.

Outcomes funds are not always able to achieve the outcomes targeted by OBC projects. The achievement of outcomes relies on many factors linked to the local implementation context and the

OBC market in each targeted geography and policy area. The capacity of local actors to administer Outcomes fund and to apply a flexible approach to learning may also affect the successful adoption of the approach. At present the evidence on the effectiveness of Outcomes fund themselves and of the contracts they fund is limited.

Examples: Impact Canada; French outcome-oriented focus on job integration, housing, and ecological transition; India Education Outcomes Fund.

5. OUTCOME-BASED CONTRACTING

CASE STUDIES IN THE AGRI-FOOD BUSINESS SECTOR

A mixed methodology was used to explore the potential of using outcome-based contracting (OBC) in the agri-food sector. First, examples of OBC around the world were identified and analysed through desk research to understand what issues they are trying to address, what actors are involved and what specific configuration they assume in terms of business models and contractual arrangements (outlined in sub-section 5.1). Secondly, a round of interviews with eminent experts in the field was initiated to gather their knowledge on how the advantages and disadvantages of OBC apply to the specific context of the agri-food sector. The round of interviews is still ongoing, as detailed in section 5.2, but some preliminary results have been included in this version of the report.

5.1 CASE STUDIES

The desk analysis⁷ on the use of different forms of OBI in the context of *food* and *agriculture* underlines that these innovative forms of contract between different actors are particularly used in the agri-food sector. The Agri-food sector plays a pivotal role in global economies, addressing the critical challenge of feeding a growing population sustainably. Within this sector, Impact Finance has emerged as a powerful tool for fostering positive change. This paragraph explores different case studies within the Agri-food sector, highlighting the transformative effects of Impact Finance. By channeling capital towards socially and environmentally responsible initiatives, different OBI initiatives have enabled agricultural innovations, improved supply chain transparency, and empowered local communities.

The Colour Kitchen SIB

The Colour Kitchen offers young adults a unique program that blends education and practical training to help them earn a diploma and secure employment. This innovative initiative, run by The Colour Kitchen restaurant, provides training for aspiring chefs, hosts/hostesses, and catering assistants. Upon completing the program, these young adults can leverage their skills and qualifications to secure positions within their chosen field.

⁷ The desk analysis was developed using a snowballing research approach and using several open access databases including the INDIGO platform of the Government Outcome Lab at the University of Oxford.

"We pride ourselves in being a place where you can be who you are, where you can discover your talents and ultimately bring out the best in yourself," says Christine de Mes, Director of The Colour Kitchen.

Established in April 2015, this partnership is governed by a four-year contract. The Rabobank Foundation, a subsidiary of the Rabobank Group, and the Start Foundation, a social investor, jointly provided €734,000 in pre-financing for this project managed by The Colour Kitchen, a social enterprise. Investors directly fund the service provider, which, over four years, educates and mentors 252 young adults lacking basic educational qualifications. The Colour Kitchen, functioning as a restaurant, educates its clients in cooking, hosting, and catering, with the goal of facilitating employment opportunities in the hospitality sector for these young individuals. The social enterprise operates multiple restaurants across the Netherlands and caters to various organizations.

Stakeholders have agreed upon three primary performance metrics, including the percentage of program graduates, the number of paid jobs secured after program completion, and the retention of these jobs. Meeting these performance targets triggers the reimbursement of the investment to the investors by the Municipality of Utrecht, with the possibility of a bonus if results surpass expectations. Initially, stakeholders set a maximum annualized return rate ranging from 2% to 6%. The municipality can repay investors using the savings from reduced social welfare expenses, estimated at €800,000. During the program, participants receive social welfare support, but it is anticipated that they will secure employment more quickly compared to a reference group.

Society Impact serves as an intermediary organization, while Pimbaa developed the societal business case that underlies the entire Social Impact Bond (SIB) structure and conducts evaluative research. Risks of failure and additional savings within the SIB are allocated among participating organizations.

SIB to prevent Type 2 Diabetes

This SIB implements a five-year intervention initiative focused on personalized lifestyle adjustments in Israel. The program will target three distinct groups of individuals at high risk of developing diabetes during the pre-diabetic stage. Over a two-year period, participants will be encouraged to enhance their lifestyles, receiving guidance on nutrition and physical activity, ongoing mentoring, and supervision from a dedicated case manager. To support this effort, the program will utilize technologies such as wearable fitness devices and mobile applications, providing both participants and managers with real-time progress analysis and immediate communication and support resources. Following the completion of the two-year activity phase, participants' blood measurements will be monitored for an additional three years, and the program's impact will be evaluated.

As one of the pioneering Social Impact Bonds in the field of preventive healthcare, this SIB is garnering global attention. Its core approach revolves around implementing behavioural and lifestyle changes that have the potential to effectively reverse diabetes symptoms and prevent the onset of the disease.

Figure 6: SIB model

Console Project on OBC

The CONSOLE project is a European funded project dedicated to promoting the provision of Agri-Environmental Climate Public Goods (AECPGs) by agriculture and forestry. This is achieved by enhancing the contractual arrangements between public administrations (at various levels) and farmers. The primary objective of CONSOLE is to stimulate innovation in the sustained delivery of AECPGs within the European Union's agriculture and forestry sectors. This involves the establishment of a Community of Practice (CoP), the creation and testing of effective cooperation models, and the development of a contractual framework that supports the involvement of multiple stakeholders.

To accomplish this overarching goal, the CONSOLE project has outlined specific objectives:

1. Develop a practical contractual framework that facilitates the formulation of improved and new contracts. These contracts will be customized to suit local circumstances, simplifying policy-making and enhancing cooperation among stakeholders, while also encouraging the adoption of these contracts.
2. Extract valuable insights from prior and ongoing experiences by conducting a structured qualitative assessment of successful, innovative, and efficient contract solutions for AECPGs delivery in the EU and in third countries.
3. Understand the acceptability and feasibility of innovative contract solutions through surveys involving a diverse range of stakeholders, including farmers, rural landowners, and other key actors in 12 EU Member States.
4. Investigate the economic, social, and environmental performance of novel contract designs through in-depth empirical research and model simulations.
5. Cultivate a Community of Practice with practitioners and stakeholders engaged or interested in AECPG provision. This community will facilitate collaborative development, testing, and

implementation of new solutions, and will contribute to knowledge dissemination through participatory co-training.

6. Ensure that the results of the CONSOLE project are practical and easily accessible to a wide audience of interested parties and stakeholders, including farmers, farm advisors, administrative bodies, businesses along value chains, NGOs, and more. This will play a pivotal role in transitioning the way AECPGs are delivered in Europe.

The CONSOLE project assembles a diverse team of experts from various disciplines and includes 24 partners across 13 countries. These partners represent different types of actors involved in AECPGs contract design and implementation, including farmer organizations, regional administrations, consultancy firms, research institutions, and water and forest management entities. The CONSOLE framework aims to facilitate the improved design and implementation of innovative contract solutions for AECPGs delivery across diverse conditions throughout the European Union.

Lessons learnt from case studies

Outcome-Based Contracting (OBC) is emerging as a transformative model in the Agri-food sector, offering a shift from conventional input-based agreements towards performance-driven contracts. While OBC holds substantial promise, it is accompanied by unique challenges and opportunities that warrant careful consideration.

One of the key potential benefits of OBC in the Agri-food sector is its capacity to incentivize sustainable practices. By linking payments to specific outcomes, such as reduced pesticide use, OBC encourages farmers to adopt environmentally responsible methods. This, in turn, can lead to enhanced sustainability across the supply chain, meeting the growing demand for eco-conscious products. Furthermore, OBC fosters collaboration among stakeholders. It promotes shared objectives and a mutual interest in achieving predefined outcomes. This alignment of interests can enhance information sharing, innovation, and trust within the Agri-food ecosystem. It can also lead to more resilient supply chains by collectively addressing risks such as weather events and market fluctuations.

However, OBC faces several challenges, notably concerning outcome measurement and data management. Ensuring the accurate measurement of outcomes, especially in the face of various external factors affecting agriculture, presents a significant obstacle. Another challenge is the fair allocation of risks between parties involved. Factors like weather, pest outbreaks, and market volatility can significantly impact outcomes but are beyond the control of farmers. Consequently, designing OBC agreements that distribute these risks equitably among stakeholders is imperative.

5.2 LESSONS LEARNT FROM APPLYING OBC IN THE AGRI-FOOD SECTOR

This section reports the preliminary results of a round of expert interviews aimed at a deep dive into the specific advantages and challenges of applying OBC in the Agri-food sector. This round included six experts identified through desk research and snowballing approach as knowledgeable informants on the topic: three of them are academics, and three are practitioners.

During the interviews, the interviewees were asked about their perception and knowledge based on involvement in previous experiences of the main benefits and difficulties of designing and realizing an OBC initiative and how they think these might change, ease, or become more complex considering the peculiarities of the Agri-food sector. The interviews lasted 30-60 minutes and were conducted by two researchers who took notes. Please note that the interview round is still in progress due to the availability of experts and will be completed in the following months. However, in this report some preliminary results are presented. It is planned to expand the list of experts by including other stakeholders who will emerge as relevant informants based on the progress of the project.

Outcome-Based Contracting (OBC) is emerging as a transformative model in the Agri-food sector, offering a shift from conventional input-based agreements towards performance-driven contracts. While OBC holds substantial promise, it is accompanied by unique challenges and opportunities that warrant careful consideration. One of the key potential benefits of OBC in the Agri-food sector is its capacity to incentivize sustainable practices. By linking payments to specific outcomes, such as reduced pesticide use, OBC encourages farmers to adopt environmentally responsible methods. This, in turn, can lead to enhanced sustainability across the supply chain, meeting the growing demand for eco-conscious products. Furthermore, OBC fosters collaboration among stakeholders. It promotes shared objectives and a mutual interest in achieving predefined outcomes. This alignment of interests can enhance information sharing, innovation, and trust within the Agri-food ecosystem. It can also lead to more resilient supply chains by collectively addressing risks such as weather events and market fluctuations. However, OBC also faces several challenges, notably concerning outcome measurement and data management. Ensuring the accurate measurement of outcomes, especially in the face of various external factors affecting agriculture, presents a significant obstacle. Another challenge is the fair allocation of risks between parties involved. Factors like weather, pest outbreaks, and market volatility can significantly impact outcomes but are beyond the control of farmers. Consequently, designing OBC agreements that distribute these risks equitably among stakeholders is imperative.

Our interviews with experts provide insights on the benefits of OBC in the Agri-food Sector and underscore its potential to bring about positive transformations in this particular domain. It was mentioned that OBC offers the potential to reduce costs, elevate outcomes, drive innovation, enhance responsiveness, and foster robust partnerships. All these advantages are further detailed below:

- *Cost Reduction:* In the agri-food sector, where margins can be tight, Outcome-Based Contracts offer the opportunity for substantial cost reduction. Providers are incentivized to find innovative

and cost-effective ways to achieve desired outcomes, resulting in more efficient agricultural practices, reduced waste, and ultimately lower production costs.

- *Enhanced Outcomes for Customers:* The focus on delivering specific outcomes in agri-food Outcome-Based Contracts ensures that customers receive high-quality agricultural products or services that meet their precise needs. Interviews reveal that this approach often improves crop yields, product quality, and overall customer satisfaction.
- *Stimulated Innovation from Providers:* In the agri-food sector, pursuing specific outcomes prompts providers to explore new agricultural technologies, sustainable practices, and efficient processes. These innovations not only benefit customers but also contribute to the sector's sustainability and competitiveness.
- *Responsive to Evolving Needs:* Outcome-Based Contracts encourage close collaboration and communication between agricultural providers and customers. This dynamic allows providers to adapt swiftly to changing market demands, environmental conditions, and consumer preferences. Interviews highlight that such adaptability is essential in an industry with evolving challenges.
- *Alignment of Goals and Stronger Partnerships:* Outcome-Based Contracts foster a deeper alignment of goals and stronger partnerships. Both providers and customers share a mutual interest in achieving specific agricultural outcomes, leading to collaborative efforts aimed at sustainable and successful agriculture. Such partnerships can result in long-term relationships built on trust and a shared commitment to agricultural excellence.

These advantages highlight the growing relevance of Outcome-Based Contracts in addressing the unique challenges and opportunities within the agri-food sector, ultimately contributing to its growth and sustainability.

At the same time, interviewees highlighted various challenges and issues associated with OBC, which are listed below.

- Building and maintaining trust among the multiple stakeholders involved in the process. Since OBC relies on the achievement of specific outcomes, it is essential that all parties, including producers, suppliers, and purchasers, have mutual trust in each other's ability to deliver on these outcomes.
- Accountability. As OBC contracts imply greater responsibility for achieving agreed-upon results, establishing precise accountability mechanisms is necessary to ensure that the involved parties fulfil their commitments.
- Proper goal alignment. All stakeholders must share common objectives and interests to ensure the success of outcome-based contracts.
- The Agri-food sector's dynamic nature necessitates quick adaptation to market changes and new opportunities.
- Measuring outcomes accurately is vital for assessing the effectiveness of OBC but complex. In the Agri-food sector many variables are beyond the control of the involved parties.
- Opportunism. Some parties may seek to exploit unforeseen circumstances to their advantage.
- Issues related to costs and staff turnover can impact the efficacy of OBC in the Agri-food sector. Costs may increase if achieving the required outcomes demands significant

investments. At the same time, staff turnover can lead to a loss of knowledge and expertise, compromising the ability to meet established objectives.

In summary, OBC in the Agri-food sector is a complex challenge that requires attention to various critical factors for its success.

6. CONCLUSION

In summarizing the comprehensive analysis of selected Exploitation schemes, several key insights emerge to inform and enrich FoodCLIC's exploitation strategy. Firstly, a nuanced understanding of market trends, customer segments, and competitive landscapes, as demonstrated by projects like Circular Agronomics and Pro-enrich, should be amalgamated with robust business model development. Emphasizing scalability, technological readiness, and market entry strategies is crucial for strategic success.

Secondly, inspired by Climefish, the exploration of advanced technological tools, such as decision support systems, can offer a competitive edge in the market. Leveraging technology for market advantages is integral to staying ahead in the dynamic agri-food sector.

Thirdly, strategic collaborations, akin to those seen in SEAFOODTOMORROW, should be encouraged to enhance resource utilization, avoid overlap, and foster complementarity. Collaborative efforts amplify impact and contribute to the overall success of initiatives.

Additionally, adopting Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) measures, mirroring the approach demonstrated by Pro-enrich, becomes essential to protect intellectual property. This safeguarding is vital for securing market positions and ensuring future commercial prospects.

Lastly, developing clear exit strategies encompassing partnerships, upscaling, and market launch is crucial for a sustainable transition from project results to marketable products. This strategic foresight ensures the continuity of positive project outcomes in the broader market landscape.

However, it is notable that the analysis conducted reveals an absence of considerations for incorporating impact finance tools to bolster the exploitation of project outcomes in the selected European food-related projects. This observation sets the stage for a deeper exploration of the concept of impact finance tools in the subsequent section of this report. The role of technology in attracting investment, especially from impact financiers, is emphasized throughout the analysis. Technology plays a crucial role in supporting purpose-driven companies, showcasing the dynamic nature of the agri-food sector.

Furthermore, as detailed in Section 5, Outcome-Based Contracting (OBC) emerges as a transformative model in the Agri-food sector. This shift from conventional input-based agreements towards performance-driven contracts showcases potential benefits, including multistakeholder partnerships and incentivizing sustainable practices. Despite limited examples in agriculture, social inclusion, and health issues, OBC presents an opportunity for aligning diverse interests and achieving specific outcomes.

In conclusion, the main findings highlight the potential for experimentation in the development of the Exploitation Plan. The analysis has revealed interesting considerations that may be useful in the development of this document. However, it is noted that there is a general lack of innovative exploitation tools, also taking into account the impact dimension of the project. Based on this gap, impact finance instruments have been further explored, suggesting specific challenges (e.g. promoting environmental sustainability, developing healthier and more sustainable food options,

promoting social and labor inclusion, and stimulating preventive action on health issues) in the agri-food sector that are suitable for support by impact financiers through outcome-based contracting.

REFERENCES

- Achleitner, A. K., Lutz, E., Mayer, J., & Spiess-Knafl, W. (2013). Disentangling gut feeling: Assessing the integrity of social entrepreneurs. *Voluntas: International Journal of Voluntary and Nonprofit Organizations*, 24(1), 93-124.
- Addis, R., McLeod, J., & Raine, A. (2013). *IMPACT-Australia: Investment for social and economic benefit*. Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations.
- Ahlström, H., Monciardini, D. The Regulatory Dynamics of Sustainable Finance: Paradoxical Success and Limitations of EU Reforms. *Journal of Business Ethics* (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-021-04763-x>
- Ahluwalia, S., Mahtob, R. V., & Guerreroc, M. (2020). Blockchain technology and start-up financing: A transaction cost economics perspective. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 151.
- Alam, M. S. (2009). Islamic finance: An alternative to the conventional financial system. *Korea Review of International Studies*, 12, 37-53.
- Alvord, S. H., Brown, L. D., & Letts, C. W. (2004). Social Entrepreneurship and Societal Transformation. *The Journal of Applied Behavioral Science*, 40(3), 260–282.
- Antadze, N., & Westley, F. R. (2012). Impact Metrics for Social Innovation: Barriers or Bridges to Radical Change? *Journal of Social Entrepreneurship*, 3(2), 133–150.
- Arena, M., Bengo, I., Calderini, M., & Chiodo, V. (2016). Social Impact Bonds: Blockbuster or Flash in a Pan?. *International Journal of Public Administration*, 1-13.
- Arena, M., Bengo, I., Calderini, M., & Chiodo, V. (2018). Unlocking finance for social tech start-ups: Is there a new opportunity space? *Technological Forecasting And Social Change*, 127, 154- 165
- Bengo, I. (2018). Impact measurement and social public procurement. *Public Money & Management*, In press – July 2018
- Bengo, I., & Calderini, M. (2016). New development: Are social impact bonds (SIBs) viable in Italy? A new roadmap. *Public Money & Management*, 36(4), 303-306.
- Bengo, I., Arena, M., Azzone, G., Calderini, M. (2016). Indicators and metrics for social business: a review of current approaches. *Journal of Social Entrepreneurship*, 1 (2), 1-24.
- Best H., Harji K. (2013), *Social Impact Measurement Use Among Canadian Impact Investors*, Final Report, Purpose Capital.
- Brest, P., & Born, K. (2013). When Can Impact Investing Create Real Impact? With Responses From Audrey Choi, Sterling K. Speirn, Alvaro Rodriguez Arregui & Michael Chu, Nancy E. Pfund, and Nick O'Donohoe. *Stanford Social Innovation Review*, 11(4), 22–31.
- Brill, J., Reder, A., & Ferling, R. L. (1993). Profit from your principles. *Financial Executive*, 9(6), 54-57.
- Brookings. (2020). Social and development impact bonds by the numbers. Retrieved from: <https://www.brookings.edu/research/social-and-development-impact-bonds-by-the-numbers/>
- Brown, A., & Swersky, S. (2012). *The First Billion: A Forecast of Social Investment*. Boston Consulting Group, Boston.

- Brown, C., Murphy, T. J., & Nanny, M. (2003). Turning techno-savvy into info-savvy: Authentically integrating information literacy into the college curriculum. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 29(6), 386-398.
- Bugg-levine A., Kogut, B., and Kulatilaka, N. (2012). A New Approach To Funding Social Enterprises, (February).
- Bugg-levine, A., & Emerson, J. (2011). Transforming How We Make Money. *Innovations: Technology, Governance, Globalization*, 6(3), 9–18.
- Carè, R., & Wendt, K. (2018). Investing with impact: An integrated analysis between academics and practitioners, in La Torre, M., & Calderini, M. *Social Impact Investing Beyond the SIB: Evidence from the Market*. Cham (Switzerland): Palgrave Macmillan, 5-45.
- Cassa depositi e prestiti (CDP) (2020). Green, Social and Sustainability Bond Framework.
- CCAF (The Cambridge Centre for Alternative Finance) (2019). *Shifting Paradigms: The 4th European Alternative Finance Benchmarking Report*
- Cervantes, M., Daniel, L., & Montalvo, R. (2017). Implementing Innovative Financial Models in Different Cultures: A Comparative Analysis of China and Mexico. *Cross Cultural & Strategic Management*, 24(3), 508-528.
- Chapra, M. U. (2014). Innovation and authenticity in Islamic finance, in Chapra, M. U. *Morality and Justice in Islamic Economics and Finance*. Cheltenham (UK): Edward Elgar Publishing, 163-192.
- Chan, H. W., Makarov, V. and Thompson, S. (2010). Beyond the "Tradeoff"; A New Analytical Framework for Social Impact Investing Industry. Working paper.
- Chiappini, H. (2017). *Social impact funds: Definition, assessment and performance*. Springer.
- Cigu, E.; Petrișor, M.-B.; Nuță, A.-C.; Nuță, F.-M.; Bostan, I. The Nexus between Financial Regulation and Green Sustainable Economy. *Sustainability* 2020, 12, 8778. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12218778>
- Clarkin, J. E., & Cangioni, C. L. (2015). Impact investing: A primer and review of the literature. *Entrepreneurship Research Journal*, 6(2), 135–173.
- Collins, L., Swart, R., & Zhang, B. (2013). *The Rise Of Future Finance*. The UK Alternative Finance Benchmarking Report. London (UK): Nesta.
- Cornée S., and A. Szafarz. (2014). Vive la Différence: Social Banks and Reciprocity in the Credit Market. *Journal of Business Ethics* 125, 3: 361-380
- Defourny, J. and Nyssens, S. (2017). Fundamentals for an international typology of social enterprise models. *VOLUNTAS: International Journal of Voluntary and Nonprofit Organizations*, 2017, Volume 28, Number 6, Page 2469
- Domini, A. L. (2001). *Socially responsible investing: Making a difference and making money*. Dearborn Trade Publishing.
- Domini, A.L., Kinder, P.D. (1986). *Ethical Investing*. Addison Wesley.
- Earl S., Carden F., and Smutylo T. (2001). *Outcome Mapping: Building Learning and Reflection into Development Programs*. International Development Research Center, Ottawa, Canada
- European Venture Philanthropy Association (EVPA). (2006). *European Venture Philanthropy Directory*.
- Eurosif (2016). *European SRI Study*.

- Fatemi, A. M., & Fooladi, I. J. (2013). Sustainable finance: A new paradigm. *Global Finance Journal*, 24, 101-113.
- Fedele, A., & Miniaci, R. (2010). Do social enterprises finance their investments differently from for-profit firms? The case of social residential services in Italy. *Journal of social entrepreneurship*, 1(2), 174-189.
- Fransen, L., del Bufalo, G., & Reviglio, E. (2018). Boosting Investment in Social Infrastructure in Europe. Report of the High-Level Task Force on Investing in Social Infrastructure in Europe (Discussion Paper 074). Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.
- Geobey, S. (2014). Measurement, Decision-Making and the Pursuit of Social Innovation in Canadian Social Finance.
- Geobey, S., & Weber, O. (2013). Lessons in operationalizing social finance: the case of Vancouver City Savings Credit Union. *Journal of Sustainable Finance & Investment*, 3(2), 124-137.
- GIIN The Global Impact Investing Network (2017). Annual Impact Investor Survey 2017.
- GIIN The Global Impact Investing Network (2018). Annual Impact Investor Survey 2018.
- Global Economy and Development at Brookings. (2019). Brookings Impact Bonds Snapshot – 1 January 2019. Retrieved from <https://www.brookings.edu/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/Impact-Bonds-Snapshot-January-2019.pdf>
- Godeke, S. and Pomares, R. (2009). Solutions for Impact Investors: From Strategy to Implementation. Rockefeller Foundation
- Grabenwarter, U., & Liechtenstein, H. (2011). In Search of Gamma - An Unconventional Perspective on Impact Investing. SSRN Electronic Journal.
- Harji, K., and E.T. Jackson (2012). Accelerating impact: Achievements, challenges and what's next in building the impact investing industry. New York: The Rockefeller Foundation.
- Hart O., and Holmstrom B. (2010). A Theory of Firm Scope. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, MIT Press, vol. 125(2), pages 483-513, May
- Hebb, T. (2013). Impact investing and responsible investing: what does it mean? *Journal of Sustainable Finance & Investment*, 3(2), 71–74.
- Höchstädter, A. K., & Scheck, B. (2015). What's in a Name: An Analysis of Impact Investing Understandings by Academics and Practitioners. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 132(2), 449–475.
- IFISE project, Multi-region assistance (MRA) initiative co-funded by the European Commission (2019). Handbook - Financial Instruments for Social Impact.
- International Capital Market Allocation (2018). Green Bond Principles Voluntary Process Guidelines for Issuing Green Bonds.
- International Capital Market Allocation (2020). Social Bond Principles Voluntary Process Guidelines for Issuing Social Bonds.
- International Capital Market Allocation (2018). Sustainability Bond Guidelines.
- Jackson, E. T., & Harji, K. (2012). Unlocking capital, activating a movement: Final report of the strategic assessment of the Rockefeller foundation's impact investing initiative. New York, NY: Evaluation Office, Rockefeller Foundation.
- Jäger, U. P., & Schröer, A. (2014). Integrated Organizational Identity: A Definition of Hybrid Organizations and a Research Agenda. *Voluntas*, 25(5), 1281–1306.
- Judd, E. (1990). Investing with a social conscience.

- Khraisha, T., & Arthur, K. (2018). Can we have a general theory of financial innovation processes? A conceptual review. *Financial Innovation*, 4(4).
- Kim, K., & Hann, I-H. (2019). Crowdfunding and the Democratization of Access to Capital - An Illusion? Evidence from Housing Prices. *Information Systems Research*, 30(1), 276-290.
- Kroeger, A., & Weber, C. (2014). Developing a Conceptual Framework for Comparing Social Value Creation. *Academy of Management Review*, 39(4), 513–540.
- Levenson Keohane, G., & Madsbjerg, S. (2016). The Innovative Finance Revolution: Private Capital for the Public Good. *Foreign Affairs*, 95(4), 161-170.
- Lortie, J., & Cox, K. C. (2018). On the boundaries of social entrepreneurship: a review of relationships with related research domains. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 1–10.
- Louche, C., Arenas, D., & van Cranenburgh, K. (2012). From preaching to investing: Attitudes of religious organisations towards responsible investment. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 110(3), 301–320.
- Lowry, R. P. (1993). *Good money: A guide to profitable social investing in the '90s*. WW Norton & Company.
- Lyons, T. S., & Kickul, J. R. (2013). The Social Enterprise Financing Landscape: The Lay of the Land and New Research on the Horizon. *Entrepreneurship Research Journal*, 3(2), 147–159. <https://doi.org/10.1515/erj-2013-0045>
- Lyons, T. S., & Kickul, J. R. (2013). The social enterprise financing landscape: The lay of the land and new research on the horizon. *Entrepreneurship Research Journal*, 3(2), 147-159.
- Margiono, A., Zolin, R., Chang, A. (2018). A typology of social venture business model configurations. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*, Vol. 24 Issue: 3, pp.626-650
- Marks, M. B. and Weaver P. M. (2017), Are Social Impact Bonds a Viable Resource for Social Innovations? A Brief Discussion Paper. TRANSIT Working Paper #13, July 2017
- Masera, R. (2010). Reforming financial systems after the crisis: a comparison of EU and USA. *Quarterly Review*, 63(255), 299-362.
- Maurer, B. (2006). *Pious Property: Islamic Mortgages in the United States*. New York: Russell Sage.
- Mendell, M. and Barbosa, E. (2013), "Impact investing: a preliminary analysis of emergent primary and secondary exchange platforms", *Journal of Sustainable Finance & Investment*, Vol. 3 No. 2, pp. 111-123.
- Muniesa, F. & Lenglet, M. (2013). Responsible Innovation in Finance: Directions and Implications, in Owen, R., Bessant, J., & Heintz, M. (Ed.) *Responsible Innovation: Managing the Responsible Emergence of Science and Innovation in Society*. Hoboken (USA): John Wiley & Sons, 185-198.
- Miller, A. J. (1991). *Socially responsible investing: how to invest with your conscience*. Prentice Hall.
- Miller, T. L., and Wesley, C. L. (2010). Assessing mission and resources for social change: An organizational identity perspective on social venture capitalists' decision criteria. *Entrepreneurship: Theory and Practice*, 34(4), 705–733.
- Muhamed Zulkhibri (2016) Financial inclusion, financial inclusion policy and Islamic finance, *Macroeconomics and Finance in Emerging Market Economies*, 9:3, 303-320, DOI: 10.1080/17520843.2016.1173716

- Mulgan, G. (2010). Measuring Social Value. *Stanford Social Innovation Review*, (Summer), 38–43.
- Mulgan, G., Tucker, S., Ali, R. and Sanders, B. (2007). Social Innovation - What it is, why it matters and how it can be accelerated. Skoll Centre for Social Entrepreneurship.
- Nadler, C., & Breuer, W. (2019). Cultural Finance as a research field: an evaluative survey. *Journal of Business Economics*, 89, 191-220.
- Nesta (2014). Understanding alternative finance.
- Nicholls, A. (2009). “We do good things, don’t we?”: “Blended Value Accounting” in social entrepreneurship. *Accounting, Organizations and Society*, 34(6–7), 755–769.
- Nicholls, A. (2010). The institutionalization of social investment: The interplay of investment logics and investor rationalities. *Journal of Social Entrepreneurship*, 1(1), 70–100.
- Nicholls, A. and Pharoah, C. (2008). The Landscape of Social Investment: A Holistic Topology of Opportunities and Challenges. Skoll Centre for Social Entrepreneurship.
- Nicholls, A., & Pharoah, C. (2008). The landscape of social investment: A holistic topology of opportunities and challenges.
- Nicholls, A., Paton, R. & Emerson, J., (2015). *Social Finance*. First Edition ed. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Nicholls, A., Simon, J., Gabriel, M., & Whelan, C. (Eds.). (2015). *New frontiers in social innovation research*. Springer.
- Niggemann, G., and Bragger S. (2011). “Socially Responsible Investments (SRI): Introducing Impact Investing.” In *Wealth Management Research*. UBS.
- O’Donohoe, N., Leijonhufvud, C., Saltuk, Y., Bugg-Levine, A., & Brandenburg, M. (2010). *Impact Investments. An emerging asset class*, 96.
- O’Donohoe, N., Leijonhufvud, C. Saltuk, Y. Bugg-Levine, A. and Brandenburg M. (2010). *Impact investment: An emerging asset class*. New York: J.P. Morgan.
- OECD (2010). *The OECD Innovation Strategy: Getting a Head Start on Tomorrow*, OECD, Paris.
- OECD. (2016). *Understanding Social Impact Bonds*. Retrieved from: <http://www.oecd.org/cfe/leed/UnderstandingSIBsLux-WorkingPaper.pdf>.
- Oleksiak, A., Nicholls, A., and Emerson, J. (2015), “Impact investing: a market in evolution”, in Nicholls, A., Paton, R., & Emerson, J. (Eds.), *Social Finance*, Oxford University Press, Oxford, UK, pp. 207-249.
- Ormiston, J., Charlton, K., Donald, M.S., and Seymour, R.G. (2015). Overcoming the Challenges of Impact Investing: Insights from Leading Investors. *Journal of Social Entrepreneurship*, 6:3, 352-378
- Palmerio, G. (2009). Some Thoughts on Financial Innovation and Financial Crises. *The AMFITEATRU ECONOMIC Journal*, 11(26), 522-532.
- Reeder, N., and Colantonio, A. (2013). Measuring impact and non-financial returns in impact investing: A critical overview of concepts and practice. The London School of Economics and the European Investment Bank Institute.
- Rizzello, A., Migliazza M.C., Carè R., & Trotta A. (2015). Social impact investing: a model and research agenda. Conference paper: Social and Sustainable Finance and Impact Investing (SSFII) Conference – Oxford.

- Ryan, P. W., and Lyne I. (2008). Social enterprise and the measurement of social value: methodological issues with the calculation and application of the social return on investment. *Education, Knowledge & Economy* 2.3: 223-237.
- Rockefeller Foundation (2020). The individual imperative retail impact investing uncovered.
- Roy, Michael J., Neil McHugh, & Stephen Sinclair (2018). A Critical Reflection on Social Impact Bonds. Retrieved from: https://ssir.org/articles/entry/a_critical_reflection_on_social_impact_bonds
- Sandberg, J. (2018). Toward a Theory of Sustainable Finance. In *Designing a Sustainable Financial System* (pp. 329-346). Palgrave Macmillan, Cham.
- Sandor, E., Scott, S., & Benn, J. (2009). *Innovative financing to fund development: progress and prospects*. Paris (France): OECD Publishing.
- Schoenmaker, D. (2017). *Investing for the common good: a sustainable finance framework*. Brussels (Belgium): Bruegel.
- SIF (2003). SIF 2003 Study
- Simon H. A. (1959). Theories of Decision-Making in Economics and Behavioural Science. *The American Economic Review* Vol. 49, No. 3, pp. 253-283
- So, I., & Staskevicius, A. (2015). Measuring the 'impact' in impact investing. Harvard Business School. Social Impact Investment Taskforce. (2014). *Impact Investment: The invisible heart of markets*.
- Soppe, A. (2009). Sustainable Finance as a Connection Between Corporate Social Responsibility and Social Responsible Investing. *Indian School of Business WP Indian Management Research Journal*, 1(3), 13-23.
- Tiresia (2018). *Social Impact Outlook 2018*.
- Tiresia (2019). *Social Impact Outlook 2019*.
- UK National Advisory Board on Impact Investing (2017), *The Rise of Impact: Five steps towards an inclusive and sustainable economy*, p.11. As reproduced from the Impact Management Project.
- US SIF Foundation (2018). *Report on US Sustainable Responsible and Impact Investing Trends 2018*.
- Viviani, J. L., & Maurel, C. (2018). Performance of impact investing: A value creation approach. *Research in International Business and Finance*, (September 2017), 0–1.
- Weber, O. (2012). *Social Finance and Impact Investing (Working paper)*. University of Waterloo - School of Environment, Enterprise and Development.
- Weber, O. (2016). Impact Investing, in Lehner, O. M. (Ed) *Routledge handbook of social and sustainable finance*. Abingdon-on-Thames (UK): Routledge, 85-101.
- Zaher, T. S., & Kabir Hassan, M. (2001). A comparative literature survey of Islamic finance and banking. *Financial Markets, Institutions & Instruments*, 10(4), 155-199.
- Zhang, B., Baeck, P., Ziegler, T., Bone, J. & Garvey, K. (2016). *Pushing Boundaries: The 2015 UK Alternative Finance Industry Report*. London (UK): Nesta.
- Zahra, S. A., Gedajlovic, E., Neubaum, D. O., & Shulman, J. M. (2009). A typology of social entrepreneurs: Motives, search processes and ethical challenges. *Journal of business venturing*, 24(5), 519-532.

Ziegler T.E.J., Reedy A., Le Bryan Z., Randall S., Kroszner K.G, (2018). 2017 The Americas Alternative Finance Industry Report Hitting Stride. Available at: <https://www.jbs.cam.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/2017-06-americas-alternative-finance-industry-report.pdf>

WEBSITES

[https://cordis.europa.eu/search?q=applicationDomain%2Fcode%3D%27agri%27%20AND%20%2Fproject%2Frelations%2Fcategories%2FeuroSciVoc%2Fcode%3D%27%2F27%2F%27%2C%27%2F29%2F%27%20AND%20\(%27exploitation%27%20AND%20%27plan%27\)&p=1&num=10&srt=Relevance:decreasing](https://cordis.europa.eu/search?q=applicationDomain%2Fcode%3D%27agri%27%20AND%20%2Fproject%2Frelations%2Fcategories%2FeuroSciVoc%2Fcode%3D%27%2F27%2F%27%2C%27%2F29%2F%27%20AND%20(%27exploitation%27%20AND%20%27plan%27)&p=1&num=10&srt=Relevance:decreasing)

[https://euneighbourseast.eu/news/latest-news/social-impact-bonds-to-improve-lives-of-farmers-in-armenia/#:~:text=Improving%20the%20lives%20of%20smallholder,Nations%20Development%20Programme%20\(UNDP\)](https://euneighbourseast.eu/news/latest-news/social-impact-bonds-to-improve-lives-of-farmers-in-armenia/#:~:text=Improving%20the%20lives%20of%20smallholder,Nations%20Development%20Programme%20(UNDP))

https://www.socialfinance.org.uk/assets/documents/food_for_thought.pdf

https://www.cgdev.org/sites/default/files/DIB%20nutrition%20briefing%20note%20for%202.24.14workshop_0.pdf

<https://www.devex.com/news/how-a-restaurant-chain-pioneered-a-social-impact-bond-to-fight-malaria-82212>

<https://www.xarvio.com/global/en/products/healthy-fields.html>

<https://www.teagasc.ie/media/website/publications/2022/Farmers-attitudes-to-results-based-contracts-and-the-benefits-of-their-adoption.pdf>

<https://www.unife.it/en/research/projects/international-projects-1/chemistry/console>

https://www.sfer.asso.fr/source/jrss2019/articles/C51_Kuhfuss.pdf

<https://www.idos-research.de/en/discussion-paper/article/results-based-approaches-in-agriculture-what-is-the-potential/>

<https://www.fao.org/3/Y0937E/y0937e03.htm>

<https://ideas.repec.org/p/ags/gewi11/114523.html>

PARTNERS

CONTACT US:

www.foodclik.eu

[#foodclik](https://twitter.com/foodclik)

Funded
by the European Union